

Women Entrepreneur Challenges and Opportunities: A Conceptual Study

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Abstract

Half of the world [population] comprises of female and with culture of various countries diffuses with each other, women entry in male dominated world is significantly increasing worldwide. More number of women are coming up and starting their own venture. As it is observed that any country's economic development is depend on the entrepreneurial activities took up by the citizen, and with the advent of women entrepreneurship, the strategy for economic development should also be oriented towards women entrepreneur development. In India women are popularly known as the “home minister” of family cabinet and took many decision related to home affairs, makes many women to easily adapt to business challenges and start their own endeavours. This paper attempts to highlight the challenges or constraints faced by women entrepreneur, especially in Indian context and also discusses various opportunities available to them. At the end of the paper author has suggested few measures to foster the growth of women entrepreneurs in India.

Introduction

There is notable contribution made by women entrepreneurs in country's economy. In post liberalization era, India has witnessed entry more women entrepreneurs in large as well as small enterprises. Women entrepreneur has shown remarkable presence in various industries like service, handicraft, exports, etc. Contribution of women entrepreneur in country's economy has shown its remarkable improvement which is evident from increasing number of women entrepreneur in last two decades.

Why do Women Take-up Employment?

- Push Factors
 - Death of main earner of family
 - Sudden fall in family income
 - Inadequate living standard
- Pull Factors
 - Women's desire to evaluate their talent
 - To make optimum use their free time or education
 - To gain recognition, importance and social status.
 - To get economic independence

Other Factors

- Nature of Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurial activity provides flexibility in time for working against the regular job. Not only that challenge offered by business ownership also attracted some women.
- Motivation: It is found suggest that women do not lack the motivation to enter into business ownership. They are often highly motivated than their male counterparts to overcome the barriers to business start-up.
- Empowerment: Indian women are becoming more empowered and laws are being progressively drafted to offer them more opportunities at various levels.
- Social Conditions: Population growth results in a strong positive relationship on entrepreneurial activity. Across genders, the increase in demand and competition for jobs pushes more people into necessary entrepreneurship. For women, in particular, the relatively high involvement in necessary entrepreneurship indicates that self-employment can be used as a way to circumvent institutional and cultural constraints with respect to female employment.
- Economic Conditions: With focus on women empowerment and creating more opportunities for women, government has announced various schemes to boost women to pursue entrepreneurial activity.
- Literacy & Education: Increased levels of education have played a crucial role in initiating the process of entrepreneurship. Proper education and congenial environment helps women to start entrepreneurial work.

Women Entrepreneurship in India

- Earlier there were 3 Ks
 - Kitchen
 - Kids
 - Knitting
- Then came 3 Ps
 - Powder
 - Pappad
 - Pickles
- Presently there are 4 Es
 - Electricity
 - Electronics
 - Energy
 - Engineering

Constraints Faced by Women Entrepreneur

In India, women are making worthy contribution in economic development, but still women entrepreneur are facing major constraints like –

Lack of confidence – Although women got competence and knowledge, but they lack the confidence. Sometimes in beginning women were not able to get the support of family in her journey as entrepreneur. So this is one of the major challenge, women has to face.

Socio-cultural barriers –Family and personal obligations are major barrier for women t o achieve success as entrepreneur, only few women can manage to balance both home and business front efficiently.

Market-oriented risks –Lack of mobility of women coupled with tight competition throws the challenge to women entrepreneur. To overcome such hurdles, women have to depend on middleman, as a result it becomes very difficult for them to market their products and make them popular.

Motivational factors – Sometimes women need major support from family in realization of their dreams, but they hardly find them, which results in a lack of motivation.

Knowledge in Business Administration – Even though women are admired as best home manager, they are lacking the skills and knowledge in all the functional areas of business management. So, every woman must undergo education to get maximum benefits of opportunities coming their way.

Awareness about the financial assistance – Government is providing number of benefits through various institutions in the financial sector to extend their support in the form of incentives, loans, schemes etc. But due to ignorance many women entrepreneurs may not be aware of all the assistance provided by the institutions. Hence women from rural and backward areas may not be able to get maximum benefits out of such schemes.

Exposure to the training programs – Though many training programs and workshops are organized by various social and welfare associations, on various skill and information on assistance available from government. But limited benefits accrued by rural and young entrepreneurs who want to set up a small and medium scale unit on their own.

Identifying the available resources – Due to hesitation, women entrepreneurs are not able to rip out maximum benefits of government schemes available through various associations, institutions, which will provide them the access to cater their needs in the financial and marketing areas.

Challenges Faced by Women Entrepreneur

1. Many girls who study well were denied of opting for further education. The parents should not restrict them and they should be allowed to choose the field of education as per their choice. In the young age itself, the decision making quality and freedom to choose make them grow well.
2. Normally, women are kept at home and they were expected to meet family needs as a result women cannot even think of doing any business. The family members should understand them and help women from their family to find their way and make their dreams to realize.
3. Another major problem faced by women in Indian society that their family members are not ready to invest money in business started by women. Sometimes, Properties in the name of male and they are not put it as security for availing a bank loan. First, the woman should defeat the resistance coming from the family members and try to convince them to support her.
4. In the male dominant society, it is not easy to enter in business field. Many businessmen do not want to make business deals with women entrepreneurs. The women have to tackle such problem wisely.
5. It is very difficult for women entrepreneur to earn confidence from bank for getting a loan, though women entrepreneurs are sincere in repayment of loan. Therefore, it is expected that the local government and banks should come forward to help the women to get loans in an easy way, without putting unrealistic conditions.
6. The women must analyse the different and small factors in business and avoid getting cheated by anybody to them in anyway, for being women. The women have to avoid bring in emotional feelings in business and try to prove that they have better management skills and courage, ready to take risk and ability to solve problems.
7. The women entrepreneurs need to prepare themselves for making business tour leaving their family. They also need to live independently and take decisions for their business. The women required to have the knowledge of latest technologies entering the business field and try to learn everything required and suitable to the present trend.
8. They should collect all information about the changes and new introductions in the business, through various mediums. They should seek the advice of well-wishers and experts in the business field.

9. The women should not deter on meeting with failure, in spite of putting Never give up attitude must be demonstrated by women entrepreneur. They should try to come up successfully again.
10. The women entrepreneurs have to regularly meet and discuss their problems with each other and share their learning to support each other whenever they find time. They should encourage many women to start their enterprise. And they have to learn new things by attending seminars and workshop on regular basis.
11. With women, it found that they are not good at keeping business secrets, so they have to maintain secrecy. They need not enter into disputes or support unnecessarily to anybody.
12. In some places, the business may be in the name of woman to avail some benefits given to women entrepreneurs and the concerned woman may not know anything about the business. Only the male persons in the family or male partners will be doing everything. The women should not allow this at any cost.
13. The women entrepreneurs should not stand alone saying that they are women. They can move well with other women and men entrepreneurs.
14. The women entrepreneurs should take care of their health. The balanced diet, regular exercise, rest and sleep are necessary for them. They should keep away from bad habits like smoking and taking alcoholic drinks, which may spoil their health and reputation also.

Supportive Measures from Government to boost Women Entrepreneurship

Direct & Indirect Financial Support

- Nationalized banks
- State finance corporation
- State industrial development corporation
- District industries centers
- Differential rate schemes
- Mahila Udyug Needhi scheme
- Small Industries Development Bank of India (SIDBI)
- State Small Industrial Development Corporations (SSIDCs)

Yojna Schemes and Programmes

- Nehru Rojgar Yojna
- Jawahar Rojgar Yojna
- TRYSEM
- DWACRA
- Rashtriya Mahila Kosh (RMK)
- Mahila Samridhi Yojna (MSY)
- Indira Mahila Yojna (IMY)
- Prime Minister Rozgar Yojna

Federations and Associations

1. National Alliance of Young Entrepreneurs (NAYE)
2. India Council of Women Entrepreneurs, New Delhi
3. Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA)
4. Association of Women Entrepreneurs of Karnataka (AWEK)
5. World Association of Women Entrepreneurs (WAWA)
6. Associated Country Women of the World (ACWW)
7. Assistance to Women Cooperatives

8. Science and Technology Projects for Women
9. National Commission for Women (NCW)
10. Employment and Income Generating Training-cum-Production Units for Women
11. The Integrated Women's Empowerment and Development Project, Haryana
12. Women's Development Corporations (WDCS)
13. Central Government Institution
14. Schemes Available through Banks State Level Financial Packages for Women
15. National Level Women Entrepreneurs Associations and Organizations
16. State Level Women's Organizations/Associations
17. NGO Initiatives

Suggestions

- There should be simple procedure of getting finance for women.
- Proper advertisement and communication of various Govt. programmes and yojna.
- Should create linkages between product, services and market centers.
- Provide Encouragement to women to go for technical and professional education.

Conclusion

Indian constitution and laws has given promise of equality to women in every sphere, but due to male dominated business world or lack of confidence from women have resulted into very limited benefits enjoyed by very small section of women from society i.e. the urban middle class women. Still large majority of women from society are unaffected by change and development activities. The major reasons behind such lagging are well discussed in earlier part of this paper. It is expected that suggestion mentioned in the concluding discussion with be given priority and concern while planning and making certain policy measures. So, it is expected that society will react and motivate many women from society to undergo entrepreneurial venture and government should come up with unaffected by change and development activities and schemes to encourage more women to become entrepreneur.

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